

Auditing Google's AI Overviews and Featured Snippets: A Case Study on Baby Care and Pregnancy

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1. Introduction

Search engines like Google serve as critical information gatekeepers for high-stakes topics where people need to rapidly acquire extensive knowledge to make important decisions. This includes domains such as healthcare, finances, and politics, where search results significantly impact individual and societal well-being (Fox, 2011; Fernández-Pichel et al., 2024; Hu et al., 2024). Among these areas, baby care and pregnancy offer a compelling example—new and expectant parents make frequent, time-sensitive decisions while learning from a vast pool of new concepts, often relying on search engines during a critical period lasting months or years. The universality and high stakes of this domain make it ideal for evaluating how well search engines meet urgent information needs.

As Google Search evolves with new components over the past decade (Oliveira & Teixeira, 2023), including featured snippets and AI Overview—direct answers powered by information retrieval and LLMs respectively (Figure 1)—there remains a gap in comprehensively evaluating their information quality, both individually and comparatively. Beyond assessing the quality of these components, research on how query factors—such as question type and sentiment—affect results remains limited. Prior studies show that question-based queries help users meet their goals with minimal reformulation (Vanderschantz & Hinze, 2017), and that question rewriting improves question-answering (QA) system performance (Buck et al., 2018; Chu et al., 2020). Additionally, query sentiment may influence the tone of responses from LLM-powered systems, raising concerns about potential biases (Li & Sinnamon, 2024; Sharma et al., 2024).

To address these gaps, this paper conducts a focused evaluation of the information quality in two modern search components: AI Overviews and featured snippets. Using the high-stakes context of baby care and pregnancy queries, we examine how question type and sentiment affect both the presentation and quality of responses, with broader implications for time-sensitive search behavior.

To conduct this evaluation, we built a pipeline involving query collection, reformulation, and algorithm auditing experiments to test how query factors influence AI Overviews (AIO) and featured snippets (FS), while controlling for variables such as location, browser, and settings. We also developed evaluation metrics and a manual annotation codebook to assess result quality. The dataset, pipeline and metric annotation codebook will be made publicly available upon publication, to contribute to further research in this field.

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2. Method

Query Selection & Reformulation

Using the public ORCAS dataset (Craswell et al., 2020), we extracted 9,516 queries related to baby care and pregnancy after filtering out irrelevant or duplicate entries, with the distribution shown in Figure 2. For the study on question types, we categorized queries into 6 well-formed categories (binary, "when," "why," etc.) following prior work (Chu et al., 2020). We then randomly sampled 100 queries per type per topic (baby care or pregnancy) where possible, resulting in 1,037 queries for analysis. For the study on sentiment, we manually selected 157 binary queries suitable for reformulation, creating neutral, positive, and negative versions using sentiment-bearing keywords. For instance, “*Can infants have juice?*” is paired with “*Is it safe/unsafe for infants to have juice?*” This process yielded 471 additional binary queries.

Pipeline Development

We designed an automated pipeline to audit algorithmic behavior in response to 1,508 queries, using agents that simulate human searches from a fixed US-based IP. SERPs were saved in HTML format, and AIOs and featured snippets were extracted and parsed.

Manual Evaluation Metrics and Codebook

Building on prior work in information quality, RAG-based AI evaluation and contradiction text identification (Lee et al., 2002; Stvilia et al., 2007; Sundin et al., 2022; Es et al., 2024; Saad-Falcon et al., 2023; De Marneffe et al., 2008; Narayanan et al., 2024), we defined two core metrics tailored to our setting. The metrics specifically assess (1) whether AIO/FS answers address the time-sensitive information-seeking needs of new parents, and (2) whether they may introduce contradiction or confusion in high-stake decisions related to baby care and pregnancy:

- **Relevance:** Assesses whether the answer addresses all aspects of the question and aligns in topic/scope, labeled as *high*, *medium*, or *low* relevance for a whole answer and assesses whether the highlighted text within the whole answer is the most relevant as a “*Yes*”/”*No*” label.
- **Consistency:** Evaluates if AIO and FS provide similar or equivalent information given a co-appearing (AIO, FS) pair and a query. Otherwise, classifies the types of contradiction, leveraging either relatively obvious features (antonymy, negation, or numeric mismatches) or more complex differences in assertion structure, world-knowledge discrepancies, and lexical contrasts and further assign the corresponding contradiction categories among *Binary Contradictions*, *Numeric Mismatches*, or *Other Problematic Mismatches*.

Three researchers manually annotated the whole dataset regarding relevance and consistency metric. The inter-coder reliability scores (krippendorff's alpha) are 0.74 for consistency and 0.95 for relevance.

3. Result

AIO and FS prevalence vary significantly by question type and sentiment

AIO answers are much more common (84% of queries) than FS answers (only 32.5% of queries), and they co-occurred in 22%. Chi-square tests show that question type is significantly associated with both FS answer ($p=0.0153$) and AIO answer ($p=0.0090$) frequencies. FS answers are less common in "Why" questions (15.69%) and more frequent in "When" questions (35.48%), while AIO answers remain consistently high (80–92%) across types (Figure 3). Query sentiment has a stronger effect on FS answers ($p=0.0001$), which nearly doubles in appearance for negative (48.41%) compared to neutral (24.84%) queries. AIO answers remain high across sentiment types (as shown in Figure 4).

While AIO and FS consistently provide answers that are relevant to answer the search queries, we observe a surprisingly high fraction of inconsistencies. Among the 322 co-occurring AIO–FS answer pairs, 32.3% of full answers and 40.7% of highlights contain contradictory information. The types of contradiction vary: Binary Contradictions (11.1%) are only triggered by binary questions, while "how + adj/adv" and "when" questions show high rates of Numeric Mismatches (up to 48.7% and 62.5%, respectively), and “Binary”, “How-to”, and “Why” questions often lead to Other Mismatches (up to 40%) (Figures 5-6).

Implications

Our findings reveal that search results frequently present inconsistent information between LLM-based (i.e., AIO) and traditional information retrieval-based (i.e., FS) answers, with contradictions appearing in 32.3% of full answers and 40.7% of highlighted content. These inconsistencies in baby care and pregnancy information are particularly concerning as they can confuse new parents, potentially leading to serious health consequences for infants and expectant mothers. Our preliminary qualitative analysis suggests causes include citing one-sided responses to opinionated questions. We suggest remedies like providing balanced, multi-perspective answers to ensure that vulnerable users receive consistent, accurate information when researching high-stakes health topics.

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5. Appendix

Figure 1: Example of Google’s AI Overview (AIO) and Featured Snippets (FS) results on a given babycare-related queries, where the highlighted text in AIO and FS suggested quite different approaches, i.e., AIO advises to contact a medical professional first while FS directly suggests a home remedy without medical consultation.

Definition of different well-formed questions – Queries are grouped into the following well-form question types and the list of keywords for certain types (e.g., the binary question group) is expanded from prior work (Chu et al., 2020):

- **Binary Question:** Questions that typically aim for a clear binary yes/no answer and start with one of the following words: "do", "does", "did", "is", "are", "was", "were", "can", "could", "will", "would", "should", "may", "might", "shall", "must", "have", "has", "had", "need".
- **Wh* Question:** Questions asking about definitions, identifications, or directions, starting with words including like "who," "what," "where," "which," "whose," "whom".
- **When Question:** Questions related to time, starting with the word "when".
- **How-to Question:** Questions that start with "how to" and typically seek steps or instructions for completing a process or task.

- **How + Adjective/Adverb Question:** Questions that start with "how" and are typically followed by an adjective or adverb, like "how soon," "how often," "how many," "how much," "how far," etc., aiming to determine degree, quantity, or extent.
- **Why Question:** Questions that start with "why," aiming to find reasons, explanations, or causes behind something.

Figure 2: Overall distribution of queries, either a well-form question or not a well-formed question (e.g., phrases) (total n=9516)

Figure 3: AI overview (AIO) and Featured Snippet (FS) appearance vs query's question types

Figure 4: AI overview (AIO) and Featured Snippet (FS) appearance vs query's sentiment

Figure 5: Contradiction Category of co-appearing AI overview (AIO) and Featured Snippet (FS) pairs vs query's question type

Figure 6: Contradiction Category of co-appearing AI overview (AIO) and Featured Snippet (FS) pairs vs query's sentiment type